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H63D Syndrome Research Consortium

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Letter to the editor

Liver conditions due to HFE gene H63D homozygous mutations are neither new nor surprising - but one symptom of H63D syndrome (type-2)

Haris Nasrullah, Atif Nasrullah, Naeem Ijaz, Umar Hayat et al. of the, Hospital Medicine of University Hospitals Plymouth NHS Trust, the Wright Center for Graduate Medical Education in Scranton, the Geisinger Medical Center Wilkes-Barre published a case study with the title "H63D Homozygous Mutation: An Unusual Cause of Deranged Liver Function Test in an Elderly Patient".¹

We congratulate on their paper and have no doubts about its accuracy. However, the authors of this case study have not expressed or overlooked the central issue: in their well-written paper they describe a geriatric case of an advanced and liver-focused case of H63D syndrome. To be more precisely, a patient with H63D syndrome type-2 without mentioning the name of the disease even once. The surprising failure of Nasrullah, Ijaz, Hayat et al. to not being aware of (or to mention) the name of their patient's disease reflects not necessarily on their work. Rather it can be considered the troubling consequence and proof on the poor state of the international collaboration in researching the many different symptoms and syndromes caused by homozygous mutations of HFE gene H63D.

Many researchers and clinicians still falsely and fervently claim that the HFE H63D gene does not play a clinically significant role. Because of this ignorance, patients die who could have been saved if their H63D syndrome had been diagnosed early. This ignorance is nothing less than a scandal. The effects of a homozygous HFE H63D mutation are known to anyone who wants to know. The facts have been on the table for more than two decades.^{4,5,6,7,8,9,10}

One major cause of this eminence- instead of evidence-based mental petrification are especially some French colleagues who prefer living in yesterday and adhere to an equally unscientific as harmful habit of being notorious grail keepers of outdated research states. More recent and more realistic findings have become available in the last 15 years.^{4,5,6,7,8,9} The principally solid work of Nasrullah, Ijaz, Hayat et al. unfortunately loses value and academic integrity, if the correct designation of the disease described by them is not amended subsequently.

It is **H63D syndrome** (type-2).

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